

CONDUCTING LANGUAGE TEACHING THROUGH MODERN EDUCATIONAL METHODS

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ABSTRACT

At the present stage, vocational education is closely related to competencies. One of the important professional competencies is digital. This is explained by the fact that modern society processes a large flow of information, which it receives via the Internet. In this regard, a modern specialist must have skills in information technology, and digital skills must become an integral part of a comprehensive education system. In this regard, it becomes relevant to develop the digital competence of specialists, taking into account the development of specific approaches to organizing and conducting training in order to develop this competence. At the present stage, digital technologies are widely used in teaching a foreign language, having their own advantages. On the rise, e-learning is helping students develop the key competencies needed to succeed in the digital economy.

INTRODUCTION

Today, innovative approaches and technologies are used in the educational process. Over the past 20-25 years, we can talk about a revolutionary intervention in the learning process of new information technologies. Proof of the latter was the teaching of many disciplines using nanotechnology, from elementary school to higher school. Young people of the 21st century from primary school to university use computers or tablets, since a significant amount of information is stored on the Internet [1].

In our context, we are talking about the educational sphere and focusing on the use of the Internet in media education. Thus, in the world of innovative technologies and in the constant flow of new information and communications, the Internet has become an integral part of human life, access to which is possible almost any time and anywhere.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Media education technologies help to combine the study of individual courses and subjects into a single educational process, since one of the main tasks of media education is the formation of general information skills, a culture of working with information, ethics and aesthetics of communication in the world of mass communications. Of course, while studying

in high school, a student can take advantage of the gigantic flow of knowledge in a certain field with the help of media technologies.

The presence of electronic media and various methods of working with them in the educational environment is increasing every day. The introduction of computer technologies in education makes it possible to increase, firstly, the motivation of schoolchildren and students to learn; secondly, create favorable conditions for independent work. Let us consider in more detail the process of motivation when using media technologies, since teaching practice shows that the success and effectiveness of any activity depends on the motivation and needs of a person. In fact, motivation techniques should be used as a fundamental basis for all activities in the classroom. The question arises about inducing motivation to learn, since motivation is an incentive to obtain the knowledge necessary for further professional activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During school, children have to study a number of subjects, the main provisions of which are important for the formation of their personality. Of course, all students have different interests. Some gravitate towards the exact sciences, others towards the humanities. In other words, some subjects are very interesting to students and the information received in the classroom is not sufficient for them. In this case, a network called the Internet comes to the rescue with an endless flow of information, motivating the student to learn new material. At the same time, the student learns to work independently, which is especially important for any person.

Modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language involve the formation and development of students' speech skills, which will allow them to become real participants in intercultural communication, which is especially important today [2].

Indeed, teaching a foreign language at the present stage is not limited to the transfer of linguistic knowledge, skills and abilities. According to foreign language teachers, successful and effective contacts with representatives of other cultures are impossible without practical skills in intercultural communication. Bzhiskaya Yu.V. believes that it is necessary to develop students' ability to participate in intercultural communication, which is especially important in conditions where there is a mixture of peoples, languages and cultures. In other words, it is necessary to prepare students for effective intercultural contacts at the level of interpersonal communication. This means that it is necessary to develop practical skills and abilities that would allow one to freely understand representatives of other cultures.

Through the Internet, students enter into dialogue, and therefore communicate. It is worth considering that the rules of language use are also changing, as new technologies and new opportunities for communication emerge [3].

According to American scientists, new technologies for teaching a foreign language involve introducing students to new communication on the Internet using ICT from the very beginning, which, in turn, will contribute to the formation of skills and abilities necessary for carrying out speech activities online.

New speech activity changes our view of language and the rules of its use. Thus, in connection with changes in the means of formatting and transmitting information on the

Internet, the processes of understanding and decoding when reading are being transformed and, as a result, the repertoire of skills and abilities needed for reading is changing. It is worth considering the introduction of some modern technical means and teaching methods into the educational process.

So, the methods of communicative pedagogy ensure maximum involvement of students in the learning process, who resort to new technologies to communicate. Web chats provide an opportunity to practice communicating in a foreign language. Internet resources are replete with accessible original materials, as social networks offer communication with real native speakers from different cultural backgrounds [4].

Let's consider distance learning forms for schoolchildren and students used in modern pedagogy. The most popular of all methods is obtaining higher education, advanced training or retraining remotely. Higher education institutions use distance learning for students using the site. The most common forms of distance learning are: watching videos, giving lectures, performing laboratory work, participating in a forum or project. The latest and most versatile form of distance learning is the forum. This type is classified into: research (data analysis, conducting an experiment by the student himself); creative (telecommunication excursions, project competitions); informational (exchange of various information); practice-oriented (publication of articles).

It is safe to say that the form of distance learning as a forum can contain a large amount of information on a certain topic, which is presented for discussion. The forum can be held with or without the participation of a teacher. We believe that such a form as a forum is very useful in teaching a foreign language and should be introduced into the learning process, since it is practically not used in teaching a foreign language.

Modern methods of teaching in higher education, including foreign languages, involve various types of distance learning classes for students. Namely:

Chat classes are classes in a chat with a teacher. All students should get involved and stay connected. Web classes are various kinds of seminars, practical classes, and conferences.

Teleconferencing is a distribution group that students use via email.

To carry out distance learning, each student and teacher has a login and password to enter the system through which the student takes tests and undergoes testing; has the opportunity to receive lecture material, assignments, video lectures using technical means - a computer, tablet or laptop. On the other hand, the teacher has the opportunity to monitor the student's completed assignments, tests, and provide educational material.

CONCLUSION

To sum up the above, we can confidently say that distance learning as a variation of modern teaching and learning methods, including foreign languages, contributes to the formation of skills in independently searching for answers, as well as learning through interaction. The main emphasis, from our point of view, should be on the interaction of students with each other.

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